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Performance Analysis of Linear Congruential Random Generator Algorithms Using Python and Java Languages

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Abstract

Giving Consideration to the era of Generic AI and Internet of things where high band width, connectivity, servers, storage and decisions play a important role. Hence speed and security is a obvious need. As pseudo-random number generation (PRNG) is also a basic need when security, probability, heuristics and many other issues are of concern. For this purpose and by considering the recent research outcomes with respect to

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programming languages like java and Python. We selected Linear congruential Generator (LCG) algorithm which is one of the popular PRNG. In this study, we analyze the performance of Linear Congruential Generator (LCG) pseudo-random number generators (PRNGs) implemented in Python and Java using three seeding techniques: manual, system time, and hash/object based. Our results show that system-time seeding offers the best trade-off between speed and randomness, with Java outperforming Python in execution times. The results noticed have proved the strengths and weaknesses of Java and Python. These findings provide practical guidance for developers in selecting appropriate PRNG implementations for applications in IoT, AI, and statistical modeling.

Keywords: PRNG; LCG; seed; occurrences; period; range; python; java, asymptotic behavior range (ABR).

1 Introduction

Generating random numbers using a computer system we have two different ways, Pseudo-Random Number Generators (PRNGs) and True Random Number Generators (TRNGs). Both these techniques are quite distinct from one another and have their own advantages and disadvantages.

Pseudo-random numbers are numbers that are generated in a way that simulates randomness but are actually produced by a deterministic process which is found in Nyo, A. M., et al. (2010), Uma Maheswari, K. M, (2018) They are widely used in computing for simulations, cryptography, and statistical sampling where true randomness is either unnecessary or difficult to achieve. The numbers appear random and lack any discernible pattern, but they are generated using an algorithm. Since the process is deterministic, repeating the process with the same initial conditions (seed) will yield the same sequence. A pseudo-random number generator (PRNG) starts with an initial value called a seed and generates a sequence of numbers using mathematical formulas or algorithms. PRNGs are algorithmically based, meaning they are predictable if the seed and algorithm are known. Used in simulations, gaming, statistical sampling, cryptography (though for cryptography, more secure random generation methods are needed), and more, a study is found in Aljohani, M.(2019),Rukhin, A., et al. (2010). True Random Numbers are Derived from physical phenomena, such as radioactive decay or atmospheric noise, which are inherently unpredictable. Since our basic concern is for computers we discuss the PRNGs and as a research study have experimented the LCG for three different seeds using the most popular programming languages, Python and Java as found in Ali, S., & Quayyum, A. (2021),Cutting, V., & Stephen, N. (2021),Mc Millan, M. (n.d.),Hugunin, J. (1997),Hoare, C. A. R. (1973),Tharp, A. L. (1984). In Section 5 of the paper we have presented experiment results and performance analysis. The study of Algorithm design and analysis is found in Sahni, S. (2004), Levitin, A. (2007),Bentley, J. L. (1979).

A. Characteristics of a good PRNG

- 1) **Uniform distribution:** The numbers should be evenly distributed across the range.
- 2) **Independence:** Numbers in the sequence should not be correlated.
- 3) **Periodicity:** The sequence should have a long period before repeating.
- 4) **Efficiency:** The generation should be computationally fast.

B. Common types of PRNG algorithms

- 1) **Linear congruential generator (LCG):** One of the oldest and simplest PRNG algorithms. Also known as LCG this algorithm has been one of the earliest and well-known PRNG algorithms. It is easy to understand the main logic behind this algorithm, and it is very fast and easily implementable too. LCGs are not applicable where high quality randomness is critical. It generates a sequence of numbers based on the formula: $X_{n+1} = (aX_n + c) \% m$, where X_n is the current number (or seed for the first number), a , c , and m are constants chosen carefully to produce a good random-like sequence, mod represents the modulo operation.
- 2) **Mersenne twister (MT):** This is one of the most widely used PRNGs due to its long period ($2^{19937}-1$) and relatively fast generation. It's the default PRNG in many programming languages, like Python's random module.

- 3) **XorshiftXorshift:** Is a class of PRNGs that use bitwise operations (XOR and shifting) to generate numbers. They are fast and simple, making them suitable for applications where performance is critical.
- 4) **Lagged Fibonacci generator (LFG):** Based on the Fibonacci sequence, this PRNG uses the recurrence relation.
- 5) **Blum blum shub (BBS):** A cryptographically secure PRNG, which is slower but much harder to predict. It is based on number theory and operates with the equation.
- 6) **Middle square method:** Proposed by John von Neumann, this method involves squaring the number and extracting the middle digits. It's not widely used because it has a short period and poor statistical properties.
- 7) **Linear feedback shift register (LFSR):** Common in hardware implementations, LFSR uses a shift register with feedback to produce pseudo-random numbers. It's particularly popular in digital communication systems.
- 8) **Cryptographically secure PRNG (CSPRNG):** Designed for security, CSPRNGs are used in cryptographic applications where unpredictability is critical. Examples include algorithms like Fortuna and Yarrow.
- 9) **PCG (Permuted congruential generator):** A family of PRNGs that offer good statistical quality, a large period, and efficient performance. It was designed as an improvement over older methods like LCG and Mersenne Twister.
- 10) **ISAAC (Indirection, shift, accumulate, add, and count):** Used in cryptography, ISAAC is designed to produce unpredictable results with very high randomness, though it's slower compared to simpler generators.

These are just a few of the many PRNG algorithms available. The choice of algorithm depends on the use case, such as speed, quality of randomness, period length, and whether cryptographic security is required.

C. Methods to generate the seed in PRNs

Generating a good seed for a pseudo-random number generator (PRNG) is crucial, as the seed determines the sequence of numbers that will be generated. A poor seed (such as using the same value repeatedly) can lead to predictable patterns, reducing the randomness. Here are some common methods for generating seeds:

- 1) **System time:** The most common method is using the current time (e.g., Unix timestamp) as the seed. Since time changes continuously, it provides a dynamic seed. For example we import time class from the from programming language standard libraries and in the body we make a call to the clock the time and convert it to integer, as given below, a statement in Python language:

```
seed = int(time.time())
```
- 2) **Hardware random number generator (True RNG):** Some systems have hardware devices that can generate truly random numbers based on physical processes (e.g., thermal noise, radioactivity). These values can be used directly as seeds or combined with other sources of entropy. Example: Some Intel CPUs support a hardware random number generator (RDRAND instruction) for this purpose.
- 3) **User input / interaction:** User behavior like mouse movements, keystrokes, or clicks can be used to collect randomness, especially in cryptographic applications. The timing of these inputs can be unpredictable and can provide a good source of entropy for seeding.
- 4) **Entropy pools:** Modern operating systems maintain entropy pools, which are continuously updated with data from various unpredictable system events (e.g., network traffic, disk activity). The seed can be drawn from the system's entropy pool, ensuring higher unpredictability.

Example: On Linux systems, /dev/random or /dev/urandom provides random values that can be used for seeding.

- 5) **Hashing variable inputs:** Combining multiple sources of entropy and hashing the result can produce a reliable seed. Example: Hashing system time, process ID, and user input together using a cryptographic hash function like SHA-256. The statements to do this are given below:

```
Import hashlib, time, os
Seed data = str(time.time()) + str(os.getpid()) + "user input".
Seed = int(hashlib.sha256(seed data.encode('utf-8')).hexdigest() , 16)
```

- 6) **System-specific data:** Using system-specific information such as the process ID, memory usage, or machine ID can add extra entropy to the seed. This method is often combined with other seeding techniques (e.g., time).
- 7) **Environmental noise:** Some methods capture environmental noise (e.g., electrical noise, radio signals) to generate seeds. These are typically used in specialized hardware systems or high-security environments.
- 8) **External sensors:** Physical sensors (temperature, sound, etc.) can provide a source of randomness for generating seeds, especially if the sensor readings are affected by natural or unpredictable phenomena.
- 9) **Cryptographic random sources:** For cryptographically secure PRNGs, a seed is often derived from a secure random number generator like `/dev/urandom` or system libraries designed for cryptographic randomness.

Example: In Python, you can generate a random seed with: `import os`
`seed = int.from_bytes(os.urandom(16), 'big')`

- 10) **Chaotic systems:** Using chaotic physical systems or algorithms can generate unpredictable seeds. This approach is often researched in physics or specialized fields.
- 11) **Biometric data:** In some cases, biometric data such as fingerprints, iris scans, or even EEG signals (brainwave patterns) can be used to seed PRNGs, though this is rare and typically reserved for high-security contexts.
- 12) **Network traffic or packet timings:** Timing of network events or randomness from network packet information can be used in distributed systems to generate seeds with variability that is hard to predict.

Each method has its advantages and challenges, with factors like speed, security, and unpredictability influencing which seed generation technique is best for a particular application. For cryptographic purposes, it's essential to use sources that provide high entropy to avoid predictability.

D. Limitations of PRNGs

The results obtained from most of the common types of PRNGs are essentially inconsistent. Some of the common limitations observed are stated as following:

- 1) Some seed states have very short periods. Such seeds are considered as weak seeds.
- 2) Generated Pseudo random numbers are usually have non-uniform distributions
- 3) They have Correlation in successive values.
- 4) They have lacking in proper dimensional distribution among the output sequence.
- 5) Do not adhere to the random sequence distribution have inconsistency in distance for certain distributions.
- 6) Defects obtained from PRNGs may go unnoticed while sometimes they seem to be quite obvious.

2 Proposed Experiments

From the above introduction and theories we have selected the LCG algorithm for four different types of seeds, Manually seeded, System time based seeded, Hash based and System specific data to conduct the experiments. We have considered the Object ID facility of Python language to initialize the seed which fall under system specific data generation for seeding and the Java language to produce the hash of Null value to initialize the seed which fall under hashing variable inputs for generating seed. Java and Python languages related aspects can be found in Schildt, H. (2007). Severance, C. R et al, (2016) The Seeding algorithms selected are simple when compare to others which need a special set up for generation of the seed. We have conducted experiments to verify the Pseudo Random generation using Java and Python programming languages. Later to measure the execution time of the algorithms when implemented and executed using the Java programming language and Python is done to observe performances of the LCG PRNGs. Our experimental performance analysis is done for asymptotic behavior range of the respective algorithms, which shows their exact behaviors. A study related to Asymptotic Behavior Range (ABR) is found in (Durrani et al., 2022b). ABR is used to study the performance of algorithmic behavior with respect to the Priori estimates specified for the considered algorithm. ABR is the range of input sample sets for which we conduct experiments to clock the execution times for the algorithm considered. The sample sets considered shall be of larger size, as we know the algorithm to behave independent of the constant factors will be bounded from below, above or from both sides. The study also focuses on how

the programming languages Java and Python influence on the asymptotic performances. As a benchmark for asymptotic behaviors we have C/C++ programming language executions which is found in (Durrani et al., 2022b). The next section shows the code of our algorithms implemented in Java and Python. We have modified the java and Python implementations to map the generated random numbers in the range 1-100 by using the modulus operator which can be clearly seen in the respective codes. Generally the PRNGs generate are to generate for larger ranges.

3 Java Code for PRNG Algorithms

The subsections A, B and C shows Java code for the 3 LCG PRNGs namely PRNG1, PRNG2 and PRNG3. Each of them being seeded Manually, Time Based and with hashing value respectively. The comments provided can be seen prefixed by // which is used to make a statement non executable. For manually seeding we scan the value from the keyboard. For time seed we use the statement.

System.currentTimeMillis(); of java to get the current time in milli seconds and to get the hash seed we have used the java method System.identityHashCode(new Object()) * 31; which returns a hash value of NULL. We have also combined this with time for a good yeild of seed. The code of PRNG1 is written completely and in subsection B and C we have avoided to write the repeated statement which are common in PRNG2 and PRNG3.

A. Java code for manually seeded LCG PRNG1

```
import java.util.Scanner;
public class PRNG1 {
private long seed;
// Constructor to initialize with manual seed value
public PRNG1() { this.seed = 1664525; }
// Generate a pseudorandom number using the LCG formula
public int generateRandom(int min, int max) {
seed = (1664525L * seed + 1013904223L) % (1L << 32); // LCG formula with different parameters
return (int)(Math.abs(seed) % (max - min + 1));
// Scale to desired range
}
public static void main(String[] args) {
Scanner scanner = new Scanner(System.in);
System.out.print("Enter minimum value: ");
int min = scanner.nextInt();
System.out.print("Enter maximum value: ");
int max = scanner.nextInt();
System.out.print("Enter number of PRNs: ");
int num = scanner.nextInt();
// Create PRNG1 instance using system time as seed
PRNG1 prng = new PRNG1();
System.out.println("Random numbers:");
for (int i = 0; i < num; i++) {
System.out.println(prng.generateRandom(min, max));
}
scanner.close();
} // end of main
} // end of class PRNG1
```

B. Java code for System time seeded LCG PRNG2

```
import java.util.Scanner;
public class PRNG2 {
private long seed;
public PRNG2(){ this.seed=System.nanoTime() }
:
:
// same statements as in PRNG1
```

```

:
:
/*public static void main(String[] args) is same as in previous algorithm */
} // End of class PRNG2

```

C. Java code for Hash value seed LCG PRNG3

```

public class PRNG3 {
public static void main(String[] args)
{
for (int i = 0; i < 100; i++) {
// Combine unpredictable values to create a Hashbase seed
long hashBase = System.nanoTime() + System.identityHashCode(new Object()) * 31;
// Perform some operations to add complexity
hashBase ^= (hashBase << 21);
hashBase ^= (hashBase >>> 35);
hashBase ^= (hashBase << 4); // Ensure it's a positive integer and in the range
int randInt = (int)(Math.abs(hashBase) % 100);
System.out.println("Random Integer " + (i + 1) + ": " + randInt);
} // end of for loop
} // end of main
} // end of class

```

4 Python Code for PRNG Algorithms

The subsections be A, B and C shows Python code for LCG PRNG4, PRNG5 and PRNG6 which are seeded Manually, Time Based and Object ID's reference value respectively. The comments provided can be seen prefixed by # which is used to make a statement non executable. For manually seeding we scan the value from the keyboard. For time seed we call the method time () available in class time of python to get the current time and to get the object ID which is nothing but a memory address returned using the Python as can be seen in PRNG6. The code of PRNG4 is written completely and in subsection B and C we have avoided to write the repeated statement which are common in PRNG5 and PRNG6.

A. Python Code for manually seeded LCG PRNG4

```

def PRG4(Xo, m, a, c, randNums, noOfRandNums):
    randNums[0] = Xo # Initialize the seed state
    # Traverse to generate required random numbers
    for i in range(1, noOfRandNums):
        # Follow the linear congruential method
        randNums[i] = ((randNums[i - 1] * a) + c) % m

# Driver Code
if __name__ == '__main__':
    N=100
    Xo = 1664525 # Seed value
    m = 2**32 # Modulus parameter
    a = 1664525 # Multiplier term
    c = 1013904223 # Increment term
    noOfRandNums = N
    # To store random numbers
    randomNums = [0] * (noOfRandomNums)
    # Function Call
    PRNG4(Xo, m, a, c, randNums, noOfRandNums)
    for i in randNums:
        print(i, end = " ")

```

B. Python code for System time seed LCG PRNG5

```

def PRG5(Xo, m, a, c, randNums, noOfRandNums):

```

```

:
    #same statements as in PRNG4
:
# Driver Code
if __name__ == '__main__':
:
    #same statements as in PRNG4 except seed value
:
    Xo = time.time() # System Time as Seed value
:
    # Function Call
    PRNG5(Xo, m, a, c,randNums,noOfRandNums)

```

- C. Python Code for object id seeded LCG PRNG6
def PRG6(Xo, m, a, c, randNums,noOfRandNums):

```

:
    #same statements as in PRNG4
:
# Driver Code
if __name__ == '__main__':
:
    #same statements as in PRNG4 except seed value
:
    variable=object()
    #Object creation Xo = id(variable) # reference value as Seed
:
    # Function Call
    PRNG6(Xo, m, a, c,randNums,noOfRandNums)
:

```

5 Experimental Analysis of LCG PRNG Algorithms

We conducted experiments to generate PRNs considering the two popular versions namely the LCG (manually seeded) and System Time Based seed. The algorithms were coded both in Java and Python. Along with this two we proposed a Third version of algorithm which uses hashing function to produced the seed which was facilitated by java language. For Python version we used the Memory Object ID as the seed. As Java language does not provide a reference of memory may due its three tier executions i.e language to Bytecode and then Bytecode to machine instruction which is found in Miecznikowski, J., & Hendren, L. J. (2002). we made used the Java's system based hashing function to produce the initial value for seed.

When all the algorithms were executed for 1-100 range we had the results shown in three tables. Table 1 shows the results when LCG is seeded manually, meaning the seed was assigned during runtime. The first column shows the experiment number, second column shows the number of unique(one) occurrences of random numbers in the specified range. Column 2 ,3 and 4 shows the two, three and four occurrences of random numbers. Though the occurrences >1 has no significance (as we have used modulus 100) it is used just for observation purpose. Similarly Table 2 shows when LCG is seeded with system time and Table 3 shows when LCG is seeded with Object ID in python and Hash value seed in Java. Also in all the three tables the experiments first 10 are Java implementation of LCG PRNG and 11 to 20 experiments are Python implementation. The Sub-section A and B shows the observations made over generation of LCG PRNGs and execution time taken by each algorithm on larger sets generation.

A. Observations made on PRNG Generations

- 1) All Three Algorithms: Time based seed, LCG & Memory/Hash based seed were executed for PRNs Generation.
- 2) The Algorithms were implemented & executed using both python and Java programming languages.
- 3) We conducted ten Set of experiments of each Algorithm. The random numbers are generated within the expected range (0-100).

- 4) Pseudo Random Numbers Generated were made modulus by 100, This was done to map the generated number in the range 0-100.
- 5) Although the numbers are within the expected range, there seems to be some clustering and repetition, which can happen in pseudo-random number generators (PRNGs) depending on how their seed is initialized.
- 6) The PRNs had about 40-45 percent unique occurrences, about 15-20 percent had two occurrence 4-7 percent had three occurrence 1-5 percent had four occurrence and negligible 5-6 percent occurrences. As discussed earlier the repetitions could be because of modulus operator which maps a number in some repeated occurrences. It is also seen on removal of modulus we have rarely repetitions. The periods found in (Priyanka et al., 2019) with respect to each algorithm actually speaks about the distance of next occurrence in the given range.
- 7) The Algorithms had no significance on a particular occurrence of integers.
- 8) The generations of PRNs with respect to programming languages had no effects, Both languages generated nearly the same way. Which can be visualized from the three tables.
- 9) Memory based and hash based seed resulted very less repetitions in range 5-6 when compared to the generations of PRNS by the Other two algorithms.
- 10) Time-Based LCG, Hashvalue-Based and Object ID- Based are faster and simpler with respect to other PRNGs. By observing the tables we can prefer time Based seeding over others. Time-Based LCG PRNG shows more trueness in generations when compare to the generations made by the other two LCGs which can be seen in Table 2 and Table 3.

B. Asymptotic measurement of execution time

For conducting our experiments we have used the system configurations specified as test bed shown.

Test bed: Memory of 3.7 GiB, Intel® Core™ i3-6006U CPU @ 2.00GHz × 4, 64-bit, 970.9 GB, Ubuntu 16.04.LTS.The driver codes for Java and Python are as shown below. The driver code are used to call the respective LCG PRNG of java and Python codes on different size of range (sample set).

// Driver code of Java

```
public static void main(String[] args){
int step=1000;
for(int n=1000;n<=10000;n=n+step){
long startTime = System.nanoTime();
// we place the call to LCG_PRNG(n)
long stopTime = System.nanoTime();
long elapseTime = (stopTime - startTime);
System.out.println(n +elapseTime );
} //sample loop
} // main body end
```

Driver code for Python

```
for n in range(1000,10000,1000):
start=time.time()
#we place the call to LCG_PRNG(n)
print(n,'\t',time.time()-start)
```

Table 1. Results of time based seed LCG PRNG

Experiment No.	Uniqueness %	Two occurrences	Three occurrences	Four occurrences
1	38	18	18	16
2	26	36	30	4
3	49	22	-	4
4	91	6	-	-
5	31	12	15	12
6	49	18	18	16
7	33	54	9	-
8	39	14	18	-
9	40	14	15	12
10	39	16	15	20

Experiment No.	Uniqueness %	Two occurrences	Three occurrences	Four occurrences
11	43	32	30	-
12	37	32	24	4
13	47	30	15	12
14	43	38	15	4
15	49	38	6	8
16	29	52	12	8
17	34	38	27	4
18	37	24	33	4
19	46	30	15	8
20	42	32	18	-

Table 2. Results of manually seeded LCG PRNG

Experiment No.	One occurrences	Two occurrences	Three occurrences	Four occurrences
1	33	38	9	8
2	36	42	21	4
3	39	28	9	20
4	33	30	15	4
5	40	38	21	8
6	41	38	21	-
7	40	34	21	-
8	45	22	12	16
9	31	44	12	8
10	41	24	21	16
11	41	38	12	8
12	31	54	21	4
13	37	36	15	8
14	40	38	12	16
15	48	40	15	8
16	36	36	15	8
17	36	32	21	8
18	40	42	15	4
19	39	24	21	8
20	46	28	21	8

Table 3. Results of hash/memory based seed LCG PRNG

Experiment No.	Uniqueness %	Two occurrences	Three occurrences	Four occurrences
1	29	28	15	16
2	31	18	12	12
3	32	22	24	16
4	49	24	21	28
5	46	28	18	12
6	41	18	18	8
7	33	20	15	20
8	48	16	15	1
9	30	20	18	20
10	45	22	18	24
11	37	26	21	8
12	26	44	21	4
13	30	40	15	4
14	40	34	18	8
15	35	32	27	4
16	37	40	15	8
17	40	36	15	8
18	32	44	15	8
19	36	26	15	12
20	40	52	9	-

Table 4. Execution times on sample sets with Python

Sample sets	Seed manually	Seed time	Seed object id
1000	0.000347	0.001145	0.000348
2000	0.000710	0.001628	0.000752
3000	0.001127	0.001707	0.001198
4000	0.001401	0.002282	0.001432
5000	0.001760	0.002781	0.001961
6000	0.002095	0.004518	0.002105
7000	0.002454	0.005922	0.002460
8000	0.002794	0.004522	0.002805
9000	0.003741	0.007555	0.003201
10000	0.003907	0.006759	0.003494
11000	0.003868	0.007601	0.003856
12000	0.004395	0.008843	0.004334
13000	0.004730	0.008305	0.004930
14000	0.005018	0.008630	0.005253
15000	0.005369	0.009650	0.005389
16000	0.006378	0.010291	0.005765
17000	0.006086	0.012412	0.006071
18000	0.006534	0.015258	0.006420
19000	0.006772	0.014055	0.007208
20000	0.006883	0.015066	0.007319

Table 5. Execution times on sample sets with Java and Python

Sample sets	Java Code			Python Code		
	Seed manually	Seed time	Seed object id	Seed manually	Seed time	Seed hash
100000	0.0747	0.0565	0.0377	0.0047	0.0049	0.0050
200000	0.1114	0.1166	0.0752	0.0048	0.0050	0.0050
300000	0.1480	0.1678	0.1112	0.0049	0.0078	0.0011
400000	0.1849	0.2319	0.1476	0.0070	0.0022	0.0012
500000	0.2213	0.2776	0.1846	0.0080	0.0027	0.0015
600000	0.2581	0.3483	0.2254	0.0104	0.0033	0.0018
700000	0.2953	0.3961	0.2697	0.0112	0.0039	0.0021
800000	0.3314	0.4664	0.3061	0.0131	0.0048	0.0025
900000	0.3682	0.5003	0.3423	0.0145	0.0050	0.0027
1000000	0.4050	0.5796	0.3707	0.0164	0.0055	0.0030
1100000	0.4498	0.6278	0.4048	0.0194	0.0061	0.0033
1200000	0.4789	0.7146	0.4427	0.0196	0.0066	0.0037
1300000	0.5157	0.7224	0.4924	0.0208	0.0072	0.0042
1400000	0.5528	0.8208	0.5328	0.0228	0.0077	0.0042
1500000	0.6024	0.8536	0.5528	0.0244	0.0083	0.0045
1600000	0.6388	0.9334	0.5879	0.0260	0.0088	0.0048
1700000	0.6766	0.9434	0.6356	0.0275	0.0096	0.0051
1800000	0.7025	1.0522	0.7007	0.0290	0.0100	0.0054
1900000	0.7436	1.0767	0.7132	0.0308	0.0105	0.0060
2000000	0.7547	1.1575	0.7355	0.0324	0.0112	0.0060

As discussed earlier in the Section 2 about Asymptotic behavior of algorithm which is achieved for larger sample sets of input size. Therefore we executed the Java and Python codes of all the 3 LCG PRNGs for larger sample sets (on different ranges). We first wanted to find the the asymptotic behavior range (ABR) of LCGs for python code which we found it to start for sample sets greater than 20000. ABR for Java code was found for sample sets greater than 200000. The ABR for both python executions and java executions can be seen from line graphs shown as Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively. For python we found the ABR for small sample sets when compare to Java, this is due to its slow performance in execution times. For Java we found the ABR for about 10 times larger sample sets this is due to its high speed of execution time. Execution time of both Java and python for a larger sample sets can be seen in the line graph of Table 5 shown in Fig. 3. Also it is found in (Durrani et al., 2022a; Durrani et al., 2022c) that Java performances with respect to execution time very good when it

implementation has less memory utilization and its performance for cases of codes which consumes more memory. In our experimental study we found less memory being used by the LCG PRNGs, hence performance of java is obvious.

Fig. 1. Shows the line graph of Table 4

Fig. 2. Shows the line graph of columns 1 to 4 of Table 5

Fig. 3. Shows the line graph of Table 5

6 Conclusion and Future Work

The LCG PRNG is one among the different PRNGs found in practice which we took up for performance analysis by coding its selected versions (3 types of seed) in both Java and Python. The experimental study showed that LCG seeded with system time has performed better than other two versions. The role of programming languages both java and python for generation has no such impact. Rather its is very clearly shown when speed of generation is of concern we have to prefer java over Python. The study has also shown the speed of generation LCG PRNGs is 10 times more than that of Python's execution time. The experimental study shall give a option for researcher in selecting the language for their experiments and in application development. We also expect that this study shall be of very much use in Generic AI and Internet of things tools.

In future we can perform the analysis of other PRNGs which have more significance than LCGs. One can conduct performance analysis for Mersene twister, Xorshift, PCG and ISAAC PRNGs. Hoping a great support to the upcoming generation,

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence)

Author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc) and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of this manuscript.

Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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